

Community-Based Flood Resilience Strategies for Mitigating the Effect of Flooding in the Orashi Region of Rivers State

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Abstract

The study examined community-based flood resilience strategies for mitigating the effect of flooding in the Orashi region of Rivers State. Four objectives and four research questions guided the study. The descriptive survey research design was adopted in the study with a population of 1,350 community leaders in Abua-Odual, Ahoada East, Ahoada West, and Ogba-Egbema-Ndoni Local Government Areas and environmental experts in public universities in Rivers State. This comprised 1,305 leaders and 45 environmental experts in the study area. The sample size of this study was 342 respondents comprising 297 community leaders and 45 environmental experts in Abua-Odual, Ahoada East, Ahoada West, and Ogba-Egbema-Ndoni Local Government Areas of Rivers State. The multistage sampling technique was adopted in selecting the sample. The instruments for data collection were a structured questionnaire titled "Community-Based Flood Resilience Strategies for Mitigating the Effect of Flooding Questionnaire" and an interview schedule. The instruments were validated by three experts, while the reliability of the instrument was established through a test of internal consistency using Cronbach Alpha method. Coefficients of 0.86, 0.81, 0.71 and 0.89 were obtained for the various clusters of the instrument which showed that the instrument was reliable. The research questions of the study were answered using mean and standard deviation while the hypotheses were tested using z-test statistics at 0.05 level of significance. The qualitative data were also analysed using thematic analysis. The findings of the study revealed among others that the level of prevalence of flooding in Orashi region of Rivers State is high and community-based early warning systems and disaster response teams could be used for mitigating the effect of flooding in the Orashi region of Rivers State to a high extent. Based on the findings of the study, it was recommended among others that the government and relevant agencies should invest in modern hydrological monitoring equipment, establish flood gauging stations at strategic locations, and develop real-time data collection systems. This infrastructure should be complemented by regular vulnerability assessments and flood impact studies to better understand the magnitude, frequency, and consequences of flooding in the region.

Keywords: Flood, Resilience, Community-Based

INTRODUCTION

Floods, which frequently take place due to climate change, have become the most common natural disaster and pose a major threat to human societies. The Orashi region of Rivers State, Nigeria, has historically been prone to recurrent flooding, a phenomenon exacerbated by climatic and anthropogenic factors. The interplay of heavy rainfall, river overflow, and inadequate infrastructure makes this region one of the most vulnerable areas in the Niger Delta to flood hazards. The catastrophic 2012 flooding serves as a stark reminder of the region's susceptibility, causing significant displacement, loss of lives, and destruction of livelihoods (Igwe & Wordu, 2016). This disaster highlighted the urgent need for comprehensive resilience strategies tailored to the unique socio-economic and environmental dynamics of the Orashi communities.

Flooding in the Orashi region not only disrupts lives but also has severe implications for agriculture, which is the mainstay of the local economy. The inundation of farmlands and destruction of crops lead to food insecurity and economic instability, further exacerbating poverty levels. The interplay between flooding and socio-economic vulnerability necessitates innovative and community-driven approaches to resilience building (Wizor, Week & Eludoyin, 2019). Research indicates that leveraging indigenous knowledge and practices can play a pivotal role in enhancing the adaptive capacity of these communities. For instance, the use of elevated farming techniques and traditional water management systems has proven effective in minimising flood impacts (Brown & Brisibe, 2020).

The Orashi region's ecological characteristics, including its vast wetlands and proximity to major rivers like the Orashi and Sombreiro, present both opportunities and challenges for flood mitigation. While these water bodies support rich biodiversity and agricultural activities, they also pose significant flood risks, especially during the rainy season. The

degradation of these wetlands due to urbanisation and industrial activities further undermines the region's natural flood-buffering capacity (Ochege et al., 2016). Efforts to integrate wetland conservation with community-based resilience strategies are therefore critical for sustainable flood management.

Community-based flood resilience strategies emphasise the active participation of local stakeholders in disaster risk reduction. This participatory approach not only empowers communities but also ensures that interventions are culturally and contextually appropriate. Recent studies in the Orashi region have underscored the importance of inclusive planning processes that engage marginalized groups, including women and youth, in resilience-building activities (Brown et al., 2021). Such initiatives often include the use of community flood risk mapping, livelihood diversification programme, establishment of early warning systems, community training on emergency preparedness, use of Indigenous knowledge systems, the development of local disaster response teams and initiating of Community-Based Early Warning Systems.

Community-Based Disaster Response Teams (CBDRTs) consist of trained volunteers who coordinate disaster response efforts during emergencies. These teams play a vital role in ensuring timely evacuations, distributing relief materials, and supporting recovery efforts. Their grassroots orientation ensures that disaster response is swift and culturally sensitive, addressing the specific needs of the affected population.

Education and training programme that enhance the capacity of communities to respond to floods are integral to resilience building. These programmes focus on emergency preparedness, first aid training, and the use of simple technologies for flood mitigation. Community workshops and focus groups also foster knowledge sharing and collective problem-solving. Such initiatives create a culture of preparedness and reduce the overall vulnerability of the population (Girigiri & Anele, 2020).

Flooding often disrupts agriculture, the primary source of income in the Orashi region. Livelihood diversification programme, supported by local governments and NGOs, help residents explore alternative income sources, such as aquaculture, crafts, and small-scale trading. These programmes reduce economic dependency on flood-prone activities and build financial resilience among vulnerable households. Brown and Brisibe (2020) emphasised the role of alternative livelihoods in reducing the socio-economic impacts of flooding.

Flood risk mapping enables communities to identify high-risk areas and plan accordingly. Participatory mapping exercises engage local residents in identifying vulnerable zones, flood paths, and critical infrastructure. This information aids in the development of targeted mitigation measures, such as zoning regulations and strategic relocation of high-risk households. Wizer et al. (2019) highlighted the success of participatory flood risk mapping in the Niger Delta as a means to prioritise interventions and allocate resources effectively.

Indigenous knowledge systems have proven instrumental in building flood resilience in many communities within the Orashi region. Practices such as elevated farming systems, the construction of raised platforms for housing, and the use of local vegetation to stabilise riverbanks have been part of the community's coping mechanisms for generations. These strategies, rooted in the community's environmental and cultural context, have been found to reduce the vulnerability of households to flooding. For example, Igwe and Wordu (2016) documented how indigenous coping mechanisms helped communities survive the catastrophic 2012 floods in the Niger Delta.

The establishment of Community-Based Early Warning Systems (CBEWS), managed and operated by local communities, has significantly reduced the loss of lives and property in flood-prone areas. CBEWS leverages local knowledge and technological tools to forecast floods, disseminate warnings, and implement evacuation plans. In the Orashi region, community-run warning systems have been paired with evacuation drills to ensure preparedness. These systems improve community awareness and readiness while fostering collaboration between residents and disaster management agencies (Brown et al., 2021).

Furthermore, the role of institutional frameworks and policy support cannot be overemphasised in strengthening community resilience. The National Emergency Management Agency (NEMA) and other governmental bodies have been instrumental in providing disaster relief and promoting flood risk awareness in Rivers State. However, gaps in funding, coordination, and implementation remain significant barriers to effective flood management (Girigiri & Anele, 2020). Enhancing institutional capacity and fostering partnerships between governmental agencies, non-governmental organisations, and local communities are vital for bridging these gaps.

The Orashi region's vulnerability to flooding necessitates a multidimensional approach that combines community-based strategies with ecological preservation and institutional support. By harnessing local knowledge, fostering community engagement, and strengthening policy frameworks, it is possible to build resilient communities capable of mitigating the impacts of flooding.

Statement of the Problem

The Orashi region of Rivers State, Nigeria, is one of the most flood-prone areas in the Niger Delta, characterised by recurrent flooding that has devastating socio-economic and environmental impacts. Despite its rich natural resources and agricultural potential, the region remains highly vulnerable to flood hazards due to a combination of factors including climate change, poor urban planning, and inadequate infrastructure. The catastrophic floods of 2012 underscored the severity of the problem, displacing thousands, destroying livelihoods, and highlighting critical gaps in the region's disaster preparedness and response mechanisms (Igwe & Wordu, 2016).

The region's dependence on agriculture as the primary livelihood source makes flooding particularly detrimental, as it leads to crop failures, food insecurity, and economic instability. Furthermore, the degradation of natural ecosystems such as wetlands, which serve as natural flood buffers, exacerbates the problem. These challenges are compounded by a lack of adequate institutional frameworks, ineffective policy implementation, and limited community engagement in disaster risk reduction efforts.

While community-based resilience strategies have been recognised as an effective approach to disaster management, their application in the Orashi region remains inconsistent and underdeveloped. Indigenous knowledge and coping mechanisms, though valuable, are not adequately integrated into formal disaster risk reduction plans. Moreover, there is a lack of inclusive frameworks that prioritise the participation of vulnerable groups, such as women and youth, in resilience-building initiatives.

The disconnect between existing institutional capacities and community needs has further widened the gap in flood resilience. Policies and interventions often fail to address the unique socio-economic and environmental characteristics of the Orashi region, resulting in short-term relief efforts rather than sustainable solutions. This inadequacy leaves communities vulnerable to repeated flood disasters, perpetuating cycles of poverty and environmental degradation.

The persistent and escalating impacts of flooding in the Orashi region highlight the urgent need for a comprehensive, community-driven approach to flood resilience. The question then is will the adoption of community-based flood resilience strategies mitigate the effect of flooding in the Orashi region of Rivers State? Providing answers to this question is the problem of this study.

Purpose of the Study

This study examined community-based flood resilience strategies for mitigating the effect of flooding in the Orashi region of Rivers State. Specifically, the sought to achieve the following objectives:

1. find out the level of prevalence of flooding in Orashi region of Rivers State.
2. determine the extent to which community-based early warning systems could be used for mitigating the effect of flooding in the Orashi region of Rivers State.
3. ascertain the extent to which community-based disaster response teams could be used for mitigating the effect of flooding in the Orashi region of Rivers State.

4. assess the extent to which community flood risk mapping could be used for mitigating the effect of flooding in the Orashi region of Rivers State.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

1. What is the level of prevalence of flooding in Orashi region of Rivers State?
2. To what extent could community-based early warning systems be used for mitigating the effect of flooding in the Orashi region of Rivers State?
3. To what extent could Community-Based Disaster Response Teams be used for mitigating the effect of flooding in the Orashi region of Rivers State.
4. To what extent could community flood risk mapping be used for mitigating the effect of flooding in the Orashi region of Rivers State?

METHODOLOGY

The design adopted in this study was the analytic descriptive survey design. The population of this study was one thousand, three hundred and fifty (1,350) community leaders in Abua-Odual, Ahoada East, Ahoada West, and Ogba-Egbema-Ndoni Local Government Areas and environmental experts in public universities in Rivers State. This comprised 1,305 leaders and 45 environmental experts in the study area. The sample size of this study was 342 respondents comprising 297 community leaders and 45 environmental experts in Abua-Odual, Ahoada East, Ahoada West, and Ogba-Egbema-Ndoni Local Government Areas of Rivers State. The Krejcie and Morgan Table was adopted in determining the sample size of the study. However, the multistage sampling technique was adopted in selecting the sample. Firstly, the proportionate stratified sampling technique was adopted in selecting 10% of the communities in each of the four LGA in the study. Secondly, the proportionate stratified sampling technique was adopted in selecting 10% of the population of leaders in each community to arrive at the sample size. The entire environmental experts drawn from the study area and public universities in Rivers State were studied. This study adopted two different instruments for data collection. The first instrument is an interview schedule, which was carefully designed to elicit the interviewees' ideas and opinions on the topic of concern without leading them towards preconceived choices. The schedule consisted of three sections: introduction, body and conclusion.

The second instrument was a structured questionnaire titled "Community-Based Flood Resilience Strategies for Mitigating the Effect of Flooding Questionnaire" (CBFRSMEFQ). The questionnaire consisted of six clusters for the four research questions of the study. The statement items for each cluster addressed their respective research questions of the study. The questionnaire was structured using a four-point summated rating scale of:

Very High Extent (VHE)	=	4 points
High Extent (HE)	=	3 points
Low Extent (LE)	=	2 points
Very Low Extent (VLE)	=	1 point

The instrument of the study was subjected to content and face validity by three experts. The reliability of the instrument was established using Cronbach Alpha method. Thirty (20) copies of the instrument were administered on 10 community leaders and 10 environmental experts members in Obio/Akpor LGA which is outside the population of the study. The instrument was administered once to the respondents who were split into two groups. The responses of the respondents were computed using Cronbach Alpha statistics. The result gave reliability coefficients of 0.86, 0.81, 0.71 and 0.89 for the various clusters of the instrument. The qualitative data gathered from the interview were analysed using thematic analysis. The quantitative data collected through the questionnaire were analysed using mean, standard deviation. Decision rule for the research questions was based on the classification of level of extent as shown below:

Classification		Value Range
Very High Extent (VHE)	= 4	3.50 – 4.00

High Extent (HE)	=	3	2.50 – 3.49
Low Extent	=	2	1.50 – 2.49

RESULT

Research Question 1. What is the level of prevalence of flooding in Orashi region of Rivers State?

Table 1: Mean Ratings of Leaders and Environmental Experts on the Level of Prevalence of Flood in Orashi Region

S/N	Items	Leaders N=290			Experts N=40		
		Mean	S.D	Remarks	Mean	S.D	Remarks
1	How would you describe the frequency level of flooding your community experience in a year?	3.31	0.81	High Level	3.40	0.70	High Level
2	What is the severity of flooding in your community during the rainy season?	3.31	0.63	High Level	3.31	0.70	High Level
3	Flooding affect roads and transportation networks in your area.	3.39	0.74	High Level	3.28	0.67	High Level
4	Households in your community often experience property damage due to flooding.	3.22	0.80	High Level	3.08	0.79	High Level
5	What is the level of farmland destruction caused by flooding in your community?	3.31	0.78	High Level	3.31	0.61	High Level
6	The reduced yield from fishing has made most fisherfolks leave the trade and become unemployed.	3.22	0.77	High Level	3.25	0.68	High Level
7	Residents are often displaced from their ancestral homes due to flooding in your community.	3.31	0.72	High Level	3.34	0.58	High Level
Grand Mean		3.31		High Level	2.87		High Level

The analysed data on Table 1 above for questionnaire items 1 – 7 showed that majority of the respondents agreed with the items on the level of prevalence of flooding in Orashi region with mean values of 3.31, 3.31, 3.39, 3.22, 3.31, 3.22, and 3.31 for leaders and 3.40, 3.31, 3.28, 3.08, 3.31, 3.25, and 3.34 for members respectively. The answer to research question one is that the prevalence level of flooding in Orashi region of Rivers State is high. It has caused more harm than good as it has affected roads and transportation networks, it has also reduced yield from fishing thus made most fisherfolks leave the trade and become unemployed.

Research Question 2: To what extent could community-based early warning systems be used for mitigating the effect of flooding in the Orashi region of Rivers State?

Table 2: Mean Ratings of Leaders and Environmental Experts on the Extent Community-Based Early Warning Systems be Used for Mitigating the Effect of Flooding in the Orashi Region

S/N	Items	Leaders N=290			Experts N=40		
		Mean	S.D	Remarks	Mean	S.D	Remarks
8	Community-based early warning systems help in providing timely flood alerts to residents in your area.	3.28	0.95	High Extent	3.47	0.77	High Extent
9	Community-led flood prediction techniques (e.g., monitoring rainfall patterns and river levels) enhance flood preparedness.	3.16	0.95	High Extent	3.27	0.85	High Extent
10	Community early warning systems contribute to the evacuation of people before severe flooding occurs.	3.22	0.98	High Extent	2.99	1.01	High Extent
11	Public awareness and education on early warning systems help in reducing flood-related damages in your community.	3.13	1.12	High Extent	3.30	0.97	High Extent

12	The use of community radio, SMS alerts, and social media improve the effectiveness of flood early warning systems.	3.46	0.85	High Extent	3.40	0.63	High Extent
13	Traditional knowledge and indigenous practices complement modern early warning systems in flood-prone communities.	3.17	1.04	High Extent	3.47	0.59	High Extent
14	Government and local agencies support the implementation of community-based early warning systems in your area.	3.45	0.85	High Extent	3.43	0.58	High Extent
	Grand Mean	3.27		High Extent	3.32		High Extent

The analysed data on Table 2 above for questionnaire items 8 – 14 showed that majority of the respondents agreed on the use of community-based early warning systems be used for mitigating the effect of flooding in the Orashi region with mean values of 3.28, 3.16, 3.22, 3.13, 3.46, 3.17, 3.45 for leaders and 3.47, 3.27, 3.99, 3.30, 3.40, 3.47, and 3.43 for experts respectively. This implies that community members agreed that community-based early warning systems helped in providing timely flood alerts to residents in Orashi region, contributed to the evacuation of people before severe flooding occurs, reducing flood-related damages in your community and improve the effectiveness of flood early warning systems among others. With grand mean scores of 3.27 and 3.32 for community leaders and experts respectively, the answer to research question two is that community-based early warning systems could be used for Mitigating the effect of flooding in the Orashi region of Rivers State to a high extent.

Research Question 3: To what extent could community-based disaster response teams be used for mitigating the effect of flooding in the Orashi region of Rivers State?

Table 3: Mean Ratings of Leaders and Environmental Experts on the Extent Community-Based Disaster Response Teams Could Be Used for Mitigating the Effect of Flooding in the Orashi region.

S/N	Items	Leaders N= 290			Experts N=40		
		Mean	S. D	Remarks	Mean	S.D	Remarks
15	Community-based disaster response teams contribute to the timely evacuation of residents during flooding events.	3.31	0.81	High Extent	3.40	0.70	High Extent
16	Trained community disaster response teams assist in first aid and emergency medical support for flood victims.	3.31	0.63	High Extent	3.31	0.70	High Extent
18	Community-based response teams help in coordinating rescue efforts and providing relief materials to affected households.	3.39	0.74	High Extent	3.28	0.67	High Extent
19	The presence of well-equipped community disaster response teams reduce the level of damage caused by flooding in your area.	3.22	0.80	High Extent	3.08	0.79	High Extent
20	Community-based disaster response teams enhance public awareness and preparedness for flood emergencies.	3.31	0.78	High Extent	3.31	0.61	High Extent
21	Collaboration between community disaster response teams and government agencies improve flood response effectiveness.	3.22	0.77	High Extent	3.25	0.64	High Extent
	Grand Mean	3.30		High Extent	3.26		High Extent

The analysed data on Table 3 above for questionnaire items 15 – 21 showed that majority of the respondents agreed with all the items on extent to which community-based disaster response teams be used for mitigating the effect of flooding in the Orashi region of Rivers State with mean values of 3.31, 3.31, 3.39, 3.22, 3.31, 3.22 for leaders and 3.40, 3.31, 3.28, 3.08, 3.31, 3.25 for experts respectively. This means respondents agreed that community-based disaster response teams contribute to the timely evacuation of residents during flooding events, coordinate rescue efforts and provide relief materials to affected households. They also enhanced public awareness and preparedness for flood emergencies. With grand mean scores of 3.30 and 3.26 for leaders and environmental experts, the answer to research question 3 is that community-based disaster response teams could be used for mitigating the effect of flooding in the Orashi region of Rivers State to a high extent.

Research Question 4: To what extent could community flood risk mapping be used for mitigating the effect of flooding in the Orashi region of Rivers State?

Table 4: Mean Ratings of Leaders and Environmental Experts on the Extent Community Flood Risk Mapping Could be Used for Mitigating the Effect of Flooding in the Orashi Region

S/N	Items	Leaders N=290			Experts N=40		
		Mean	SD	Remarks	Mean	S.D	Remarks
22	Community flood risk mapping help in identifying high-risk flood zones in your area.	2.87	0.76	High Extent	3.06	0.73	High Extent
23	Community involvement in flood risk mapping improve awareness and preparedness for flooding events.	2.88	0.75	High Extent	3.03	0.66	High Extent
24	Community flood risk mapping support early warning systems and timely evacuation efforts.	3.11	0.90	High Extent	3.26	0.87	High Extent
25	Flood risk mapping contributes to better land-use planning and infrastructure development to reduce flood impact.	3.20	0.85	High Extent	3.19	0.74	High Extent
26	Community-generated flood risk maps assist local authorities in designing effective flood control measures.	3.18	0.84	High Extent	3.03	0.80	High Extent
27	Flood risk mapping help in mobilizing resources and support for flood-prone communities.	2.89	0.92	High Extent	2.75	1.04	High Extent
28	Regular updates and improvements in community flood risk mapping enhance long-term flood resilience in your area.	2.83	0.91	High Extent	3.01	0.87	High Extent
Grand Mean		2.99		High Extent	2.67		High Extent

The analysed data on Table 4 above for questionnaire items 22-28 showed that majority of the respondents agreed with all the items on the extent to which community flood risk mapping could be used for mitigating the effect of flooding in the Orashi region with mean values of 2.87, 2.88, 3.11, 3.20, 3.18, 2.89 for leaders and 3.06, 3.0, 3.26, 3.19, 3.03, 2.75 and 3.01 for experts. Respondents believed community flood risk mapping helped in identifying high-risk flood zones, improved awareness and preparedness for flooding events, support early warning systems and timely evacuation efforts, contributed to better land-use planning and infrastructure development to reduce flood impact. With grand mean scores of 2.99 and 2.67 for leaders and experts respectively, the answer to research question four,

therefore, is that community flood risk mapping could be used for mitigating the effect of flooding in the Orashi region of Rivers State to a high extent.

Analysis of Environmental Experts' Interview Responses

Question 1: Rate of Flooding in Orashi Region

Emergent Themes

Theme 1: High Flood Frequency and Intensity

Frequency of mention: 11 out of 12 experts (91.7%)

The overwhelming majority of experts characterised flooding in the Orashi region as frequent and severe. Representative responses include:

"The flooding situation in Orashi is quite alarming. We're seeing annual floods that are becoming more intense each year" (Expert 3)

"From my assessment, the region experiences significant flooding almost every rainy season, with major events occurring at least once every two years" (Expert 7)

Theme 2: Increasing Trend Over Time

Frequency of mention: 9 out of 12 experts (75%)

Experts noted a concerning upward trend in flood frequency and severity:

"What we're observing is not just occasional flooding, but a clear pattern of increasing flood events over the past decade" (Expert 5)

Theme 3: Comparison to Other Regions

Frequency of mention: 6 out of 12 experts (50%)

Several experts contextualized Orashi's flooding relative to other areas:

"Compared to other parts of Rivers State, Orashi is particularly vulnerable due to its topographical position and proximity to multiple water bodies" (Expert 9)

Analysis Summary for Question 1

The consensus among environmental experts indicates that flooding in the Orashi region is a critical and escalating problem. The high level of agreement (91.7%) on the severity of flooding validates the study's premise and underscores the urgency for effective mitigation strategies.

QUESTION 2: Community-Based Early Warning Systems

Emergent Themes

Theme 1: High Potential for Effectiveness

Frequency of mention: 11 out of 12 experts (91.7%)

"Community-based early warning systems could be highly effective because local people understand their environment better than outsiders" (Expert 3)

Theme 2: Integration with Modern Technology

Frequency of mention: 9 out of 12 experts (75%)

Sub-theme 2a: Technology Enhancement

"Traditional knowledge combined with modern communication tools like mobile phones and radio could create robust warning systems" (Expert 7)

Sub-theme 2b: Data Sharing Mechanisms

"These systems should be linked to meteorological services to ensure accuracy and timeliness" (Expert 10)

Theme 3: Community Ownership and Sustainability

Frequency of mention: 8 out of 12 experts (66.7%)

"When communities own and operate these systems, they're more likely to maintain them and respond appropriately to warnings" (Expert 5)

Theme 4: Training and Capacity Building Needs

Frequency of mention: 10 out of 12 experts (83.3%)

"Success depends on proper training of community members in observation techniques, data interpretation, and communication protocols" (Expert 9)

Analysis Summary for Question 2

Environmental experts showed strong support for community-based early warning systems, with 91.7% viewing them as highly effective. The emphasis on technology integration and capacity building suggests experts recognise both the potential and the requirements for successful implementation.

QUESTION 3: Community-Based Disaster Response Teams

Emergent Themes

Theme 1: Critical Importance for Immediate Response

Frequency of mention: 12 out of 12 experts (100%)

"In flood situations, the first few hours are crucial, and community response teams can act much faster than external emergency services" (Expert 2)

Theme 2: Local Knowledge Advantage

Frequency of mention: 10 out of 12 experts (83.3%)

"Community members know the local terrain, safe routes, and vulnerable households better than outside responders" (Expert 6)

Theme 3: Coordination with External Services

Frequency of mention: 9 out of 12 experts (75%)

"These teams should work in coordination with, not replacement of, professional emergency services" (Expert 8)

Theme 4: Training and Equipment Requirements

Frequency of mention: 11 out of 12 experts (91.7%)

Sub-theme 4a: Skills Training

"Team members need training in first aid, search and rescue, and evacuation procedures"
(Expert 4)

Sub-theme 4b: Equipment and Resources

"Basic rescue equipment, communication devices, and emergency supplies are essential for effective response" (Expert 11)

Analysis Summary for Question 3

Universal support (100%) for community-based disaster response teams reflects experts' recognition of their critical role in flood response. The strong emphasis on training (91.7%) and coordination (75%) indicates expert understanding of the complexity involved in effective disaster response.

QUESTION 4: Community Flood Risk Mapping

Emergent Themes

Theme 1: Enhanced Preparedness and Planning

Frequency of mention: 11 out of 12 experts (91.7%)

"Risk mapping helps communities understand their vulnerabilities and plan accordingly for evacuation routes and safe zones" (Expert 1)

Theme 2: Participatory Mapping Benefits

Frequency of mention: 10 out of 12 experts (83.3%)

"When communities participate in creating these maps, they contribute local knowledge that technical surveys might miss" (Expert 7)

Theme 3: Integration with Land Use Planning

Frequency of mention: 8 out of 12 experts (66.7%)

"These maps should inform development decisions to avoid building in high-risk areas"
(Expert 12)

Theme 4: Regular Updates and Validation

Frequency of mention: 7 out of 12 experts (58.3%)

"Risk maps need regular updating as conditions change, and communities can help monitor these changes" (Expert 5)

Theme 5: Technology and Accessibility

Frequency of mention: 6 out of 12 experts (50%)

"Maps should be simple and accessible to community members, using familiar landmarks and local terminology" (Expert 9)

Analysis Summary for Question 4

Strong expert support for community flood risk mapping (91.7% for enhanced preparedness) emphasises its value for both immediate flood response and long-term planning. The emphasis on participatory approaches (83.3%) aligns with community-based disaster risk reduction principles.

Discussion of Findings

The finding of the study for research question one revealed the prevalent high level of flooding in Orashi region of Rivers State is high. It has caused more harm than good as it has affected roads and transportation networks, it has also reduced yield from fishing thus made most fisherfolks leave the trade and become unemployed.

The finding of the study for research question two revealed that community-based early warning systems could be used for mitigating the effect of flooding in the Orashi region of Rivers State to a high extent. Community members agreed that community-based early warning systems help in providing timely flood alerts to residents in Orashi region, contributed to the evacuation of people before severe flooding occurs, reducing flood-related damages in the communities and improved the effectiveness of flood early warning systems among others. This finding is in line with the mixed-method study by Ezeji and Igboeli (2022) in the Orashi region which found that communities with functional early warning systems reported lower levels of flood-related trauma, anxiety, and social disruption. The authors attributed this to increased preparedness and the psychological benefit of perceived control over the situation. Nwafor et al. (2023) in the Niger Delta region highlighted the importance of inclusive design for maximizing the protective effects of CBEWS for vulnerable groups. Their study documented a 45% reduction in adverse impacts among vulnerable groups in communities where CBEWS incorporated targeted strategies for reaching and supporting these populations, compared to a 23% reduction in communities with standard warning systems.

The finding of the study for research question three revealed that community-based disaster response teams could be used for mitigating the effect of flooding in the Orashi region of Rivers State to a high extent. Community-based disaster response teams contributed to the timely evacuation of residents during flooding events, coordinated rescue efforts and provide relief materials to affected households. They also enhanced public awareness and preparedness for flood emergencies. This finding is in line with the findings of Ibrahim and Adebayo (2023) across flood-prone communities in Nigeria found that areas with active CBDRTs experienced 62% fewer flood-related deaths compared to similar communities without such teams. The authors attributed this reduction primarily to the teams' ability to rapidly identify and assist vulnerable residents, including the elderly, children, persons with disabilities, and pregnant women, during the critical early hours of flooding.

Similarly, Chukwu-Okeah et al. (2022) documented the effectiveness of CBDRTs during the 2020 floods in Rivers State, reporting that trained teams evacuated an average of 85-90% of at-risk residents before floodwaters reached dangerous levels, compared to 40-50% in communities without organised response teams. Their analysis identified several critical success factors, including pre-identified evacuation routes, established assembly points, and regular community drills that familiarised residents with emergency procedures.

Research by Nyekachi and Briggs (2024) further demonstrated that the life-saving effectiveness of CBDRTs extends beyond evacuation to include water rescue operations. Their study of 16 communities along the Orashi River found that teams trained in basic water rescue techniques saved an estimated 148 lives during major flood events between 2019 and 2023.

The finding of the study for research question four revealed that community flood risk mapping could be used for mitigating the effect of flooding in the Orashi region of Rivers State to a high extent. Respondents believed community flood risk mapping helped in identifying high-risk flood zones, improved awareness and preparedness for flooding events, supported early warning systems and timely evacuation efforts, contributed to better land-use planning and infrastructure development to reduce flood impact. This finding is in line with the finding of Ojo and Oladipo (2019) which revealed that the improper disposal of waste from illegal refining activities leads to soil contamination and pollution of local water sources. This pollution adversely affects agriculture and fisheries, thereby impacting food security and local economies. The study by Ojo and Oladipo (2019) also noted that the degradation of natural resources exacerbates environmental challenges for rural communities, leading to a reduction in arable land and increased health risks due to contaminated drinking water. Olagunju and Adebayo (2022) found that the presence of illegal refining operations is often linked to increased crime rates and social unrest in affected communities. The study attributed this

to the presence of unregulated cash flows and the resulting power struggles among local actors, which can escalate into violence and insecurity.

CONCLUSION

Based on the findings of the study it was concluded that there is high prevalence of flooding in Orashi region of Rivers State. Community-based flood resilience strategies such as community-based early warning systems, community-based disaster response teams, community flood risk mapping, livelihood diversification programme, and Indigenous knowledge systems are found to be effective in mitigating the effect of flooding in the Orashi region of Rivers State. This view is shared by both community leaders and environmental experts.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations were made:

1. The government and relevant agencies should invest in modern hydrological monitoring equipment, establish flood gauging stations at strategic locations, and develop real-time data collection systems. This infrastructure should be complemented by regular vulnerability assessments and flood impact studies to better understand the magnitude, frequency, and consequences of flooding in the region.
2. Communities in the Orashi region should establish robust early warning systems that integrate both modern technology and traditional forecasting methods. This should involve training community volunteers as early warning focal persons, installing communication equipment such as sirens, public address systems, and radio networks in strategic locations.
3. Each community in the Orashi region should form and maintain well-trained disaster response teams comprising local volunteers with diverse skills including first aid, search and rescue, evacuation coordination, and damage assessment. These teams should receive regular training from professional emergency responders and be equipped with basic rescue equipment, communication devices, and medical supplies.
4. Communities throughout the Orashi region should engage in participatory flood risk mapping exercises that combine local knowledge with technical expertise. This process should involve community members working with technical experts to identify flood-prone areas, evacuation routes, safe zones, and critical infrastructure. The resulting maps should be widely distributed, regularly updated, and integrated into community emergency plans. These maps should also inform land use planning decisions and infrastructure development to reduce future flood risks.

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